

SELF-HELP GROUPS AS A CATALYST FOR MARKETING EMPOWERMENT: BINARY LOGISTIC REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF WOMEN-OWNED BUSINESSES

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: *The study attempts to answer the question; Do self-help groups predict marketing empowerment?*

Methodology: *This study used positivism paradigm to test the significant influence of self-help groups on marketing empowerment. Questionnaires were used to capture data for statistical analysis. Women-owned businesses were targeted population of this study. Simple random sampling was used to draw a sample from 383 respondents. Data was collected in the Shinyanga region of Tanzania. Binary logistic regression was used to analyze the data of this study because dependent variable was binary.*

Findings: *Findings indicated that self-help groups are a significant catalyst on influencing marketing empowerment in women-owned businesses. Additionally, savings, credit and social capital were found to account for the explanatory power of self-help groups in explaining women's marketing empowerment. It is concluded that self-help groups are a key catalyst for marketing empowerment.*

Practical Implications: *Leveraging the World Values Survey, this study shows that self-help groups have significant power to empower women in the marketing of their business enterprises through saving, credit and social capital. This shows an unusual marketing performance indicating that women who are members of self-help groups have a large chance to perform in marketing when they access more services from self-help groups regardless of the limitations they have in the social structure.*

Originality/value: *The current study makes a substantial contribution to the current literature on linking self-help groups and marketing empowerment. It breaks ground by being the first tract that examines, using empowerment theory, self-help and logistic regression models in Tanzania.*

Key words: *Self Help Groups, Market Empowerment, Binary Logistic Regression*

Paper type: *Research paper*

1. INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, women empowerment has been considered a core concept in emerging market economies since the 1980s and, currently, it is well emphasized in the third Millennium Development Goals. Women are considered in empowerment initiatives because existing norms and culture has continuously undermined women in all spheres of life and in efforts towards their business marketing success (Arellano-Hernandez, 2018; Tabassum, *et al.*, 2019). These norms and culture tend to limit women from exploring the potential of business opportunities and from winning business competitions. Agarwal, *et al.*, (2016) pointed out that women are not performing in the current market conditions due to many factors hindering their activeness in their participation in economic activities. To address all spheres that undermine women and limit their success, scholars such as Nithyanandhan and Mansor (2015) have argued that marketing empowerment initiatives have to be in place to enable women to cope with the existing business competition in efforts to advance their wellbeing and participate in economic activities. As argued by Geetha and Dhanasekaran (2021) women are important in any economy and in all development initiatives, and for the growth of a country women are considered important. Hence, women marketing empowerment is important in all spheres of development and business marketing performances.

However, how women are to be empowered in the business sector and other areas is still a difficult question to answer. Recent policy and empirical evidence have recognized self-help group to be an efficient strategy to empower women in business marketing. Notably, Archana and Gnanaprakasam (2018) advocate that the self-help group is a tool enabling income generation and it is a vehicle for the economic empowerment of women through multi-dimensional approaches. They added that the self-help group is designed to focus on all domains of development for transforming the economic and social sphere toward a better life. On the other hand, Geetha and Dhanasekaran (2021) argued that, women empowerment is a collective idea and a self-help group is an instrumental tool in empowering women in several areas. Mtenga (2018) found and concluded that self-help groups are a mechanism to improve the life of the poor and a way to transform women's life to achieve a better social and economic domain in Tanzania. The author added that the self-helps group forms an important vehicle where members can join together for mutual benefits of their livelihood in several aspects of life.

In realizing the importance of empowering women through self-help groups, both developed and developing nations have put a lot of initiatives to empower women through self-help group in business market environment. For example, Nirmala and Yepthomi (2014) shows in their study that the government of India initiated self-help groups (SHGs) programme as a strategy for marginalized groups to cope with economic changes, and to transform their wellbeing toward financial inclusion. As a result, the number of women financed by banks through self-help groups has grown annually.

Despite the importance of women empowerment through self-help groups and initiatives done by governments, a number of women who have joined self-help groups still find their business markets are still locked. Further, in spite of the volume of literature available linking self-help groups to empowerment, empirical evidence linking self-help groups to women marketing empowerment is very minimal. Moreover, policymakers and governments, in general, view SHGs favorably but studies show debate in the sense that scholars are using different dimensions to explain the influence of the self-help group. For example, Palani and Balamurugan (2016) found and concluded that self-help group have had significant impact on several aspects including economic and social aspects of the beneficiaries while Brody et. Al., (2016) found and concluded that women in SHGs are benefiting from psychological empowerment. Therefore, it is not clear whether the self-help group can influence women marketing empowerment using one dimension or not. This study envisages to provide evidence based approaches to fill the gap by analyzing the relationship between Self-Help Groups and marketing empowerment among women-owned businesses in Tanzania.

2. REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

2.1 Key Concept

2.1.1 Self Help Group

Vasantha (2015) defined the self-help groups as a small group of 12 to 20 poor women organized in informal association for achieving a common economic goal. On the other hand, Archana and Gnanaprakasam (2018) defined the self-help groups as a tiny group of individuals who willingly join together and create an association for attaining a general goal. According to Nithyanandhan and Mansor (2015) self-help groups (SHGs) is an informal association designed to enable members to benefit through joint responsibility and mutual help. In this study, the self-help groups are the informal financial association consisting of members who are women whose target is to exploit business opportunities through solidarity, mutual help and joint responsibility.

2.1.2 Women Empowerment

According to Agarwal, *et al.* (2016) women empowerment is defined as a way of granting financial and non-financial support to women to enable them to decide and transform for their own lives socially. On the other hand, Nithyanandhan and Mansor (2015) defined women's empowerment as a strategy which enables women to cope with existing norms and culture in efforts to advance and promote their wellbeing. Lungbila (2016) state that empowerment is a mechanism where people gain ability over decisions about transformation of their own lives. In this study, women empowerment is considered to be a strategic procedure that helps women to be able to decide and gain control over their economy in particular marketing conditions.

2.2 Theoretical Literature Review

According to Perkins and Zimmerman et. Al., (1995) empowerment theory states that intervention methods are designed to enable people to be able to control their resources by making their own decision in achieving a better life. Empowerment theory focuses on how

people can access a better life through their little resources they have through joint responsibility. On the other hand, for Zimmerman, *et al.* (1992) empowerment theory focus on the co-creation of knowledge and emphasizes the participation of patients. In this study, intervention methods such as the self-help groups are assessed on how it guides women toward achieving a sense of control of their marketing environment.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Sidhu, *et al.* (2019) carried out a study to link self-help groups and the empowerment of women in Punjab. Their findings revealed that the self-help groups only offers significant empowerment in the economic dimensions more specifically in supporting income generating activities among women in Punjab. On the other hand, Kumar (2018) in his study on the effect of self-help group on the marketing empowerment among women in Patna District. Found that women who are members of the self-help groups found their income had increased after joining SHG. The increase in income had helped in promotion of business activities to a great extent in several families. Further, Badejo, *et al.* (2017) carried out a study on the impact of self-help groups on pastoral women's empowerment in Nigeria. The findings show that groups promoting social, physical and psychological health strongly motivated women's involvement in self-help groups. Self-help activities showed commitment to effect a change in their livelihoods, despite constraining environmental, cultural and social factors. Engagement of women's self-help groups in livestock development programmes offers a powerful instrument for driving forward the One Health practice in pastoralist communities, promoting human, animal and environmental health and well-being. Verma (2019) carried out a study on relationship between self-help groups and women empowerment. The study found that SHG has led to many achievements in all domains of empowerment for those women.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

In this study, the framework was designed to link self-help groups and women marketing empowerment as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Constructed by author based on literature review (2022)

3. METHODS

This study used positivism paradigm to test the existence of the relationship between self-help groups and women marketing empowerment. Questionnaires were used to collect data for

statistical analysis. Women business owners and who are currently enjoying services from self-help group were the targeted population of this study. The owners were considered to be suitable as they are the decision makers of their enterprises by joining self-help group and in the market operation of their businesses. A simple random technique was carried out as a sampling method to draw a sample size of 382 respondents in the tourism sector. Data was collected in the Shinyanga region in Tanzania. This area was selected because the existence of the self-help group comprises of women and business marketing activities. Validity was ensured using a pilot study. Logistic regression was carried out to test the existence of significant influence among variables in the conceptual framework.

4. FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

In analysis of the study objective, tables have been produced to show the findings from the binary logistic regression as follows.

Table 1 Percent of Model Variance Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	494.826 ^a	.077	.104

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

In table 1 the explained variation in the dependent variable, namely marketing empowerment, based on our model ranges from 10.4.0% to 7.7% as indicated in the Cox & Snell R Square and Nagelkerke R Square values of the table column.

Apart from that, Table 2 below shows the contribution of Self Help Group to marketing empowerment.

Table 2 Path Coefficient Between Self Help Groups and Marketing Empowerment

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	REMARKS
Step 0 Constant	-.236	.103	5.263	1	.022	Accepted

In table 2 above, the significant value is accepted and the model has produced a significant value of 0.022 which is at the acceptable range of being less than 0.05. The statistical significance of an independent variable namely self-help group is found in the "Sig." column where self-help group on market empowerment was found to have a significant p-value ($p = .022$). This implies that increasing women's participation in a self-help group is predicting an increased likelihood of women marketing empowerment.

On the other hand, table 3 shows the explanatory power of each indicators variable of self-help group in predicting marketing empowerment.

Table 3 Path Coefficient of Indicators Variables

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	REMARKS
Saving	.445	.160	7.714	1	.005	Accepted
Credit	-.495	.144	11.890	1	.001	Accepted
Step 1 ^a Social Capital	.267	.138	3.776	1	.052	Accepted
Income	.227	.122	3.484	1	.062	Rejected
Constant	-1.895	.705	7.232	1	.007	.150

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Saving, Credit, Social Capital, Income.

In table 3 it can be see that saving ($p = .005$), credit ($p = .001$) and social capital($p = .052$) have significant contribution to the model while income ($p = .062$) did not add significantly to the model.

5. DISCUSSION

The study findings indicate that the self-help group is a significant catalyst in marketing empowerment by yielding a significant value (sign) less or equal to 0.05 in a logistic regression model which was statistically significant due to the explanatory power of saving credit and social capital. These findings support the argument made by Shrestha (2022) that women who are members of SHGs have been enjoying more empowered compared to their previous life before joining the self-help group. Furthermore, findings from the current study have supported the study findings by Nayak and Panigrahi (2020) who found and suggested that when the number of women is higher in SHGs operation, this will result in an improved entrepreneurial ability which in turn will bring employment opportunities and higher income. On the other hand, Nirmala and Yepthomi (2014) found that credit from SHGs tend to enhance the financial access of the women entrepreneurs by enabling them to access investment facilities, training and business service support. These findings imply that when women owned business are exposed to SHGs, they will automatically gradually be empowered in all business spheres where marketing empowerment is inclusive.

While the current study findings were found to be similar with findings from previous studies (Al-Kubati and Selvaratnam, 2021; Kumar, 2018) they, however, differ in terms of explanation of the significant influence of SHGs on empowerment. The current study is explains the significant influence of SHGs in terms of saving, credit and social capital on empowerment while Al-Kubati and Selvaratnam (2021) found that the self- help groups is a tool for women empowerment and is a facilitator of entrepreneurial activities through the provision of technical skills and market access. On the other hand, Kumar (2018) explained that SHGs have helped to produce assets and have transformed the living conditions of the members for the best. He added that it has also helped to change their social outlook and attitudes. This implies that the different observed study findings in explaining the significant influence of SHGs are based on the

contextual differences between one study and another. Further, it implies that SHGs can be explained using mixed results due to the contextual difference between one study and other.

In unrelated perspective, the current study did not support the influence of income generated by SHGs on empowerment which is supported by previous studies. Notably, Vasantha (2015) found and argued that the income generated through SHG are sources of business opportunity and capital formation among women. Ravindra and Tiwari (2016) reiterates that SHGs are appreciated as useful tools helping women accessing financial resources as income, which was not available to them. These findings imply that income as a measure of SHGs is not always supporting empowerment in all contexts but is still important in some contexts.

The focus of the current study was on marketing empowerment but prior studies have touched other spheres of marketing empowerment where SHGs are supporting. For example for Brody et. Al., (2016) evidence suggests that the effects of SHGs on women is observed in social and political sectors through improved social networks. On the contrary, Shrestha (2022) found that the influence of women membership in SHGs is more active in the social and cultural domain. Nayak and Panigrahi (2020) found that a higher participation in SHGs tends to improve decision making capabilities which in turn increases access to quality health care, communication skills and the ability to transact with banks. This implies that marketing empowerment can happen using different spheres such as social, economic and cultural spheres.

6. CONCLUSION

While the self-help groups were found to be significant in empowering business women in their market operation, this concludes that the self-help groups are the catalyst for marketing empowerment among women in Tanzania. While income was found to be insignificant in explaining the influence of the self- help groups in marketing empowerment, it can be concluded that in this study only saving, credit and social capital offered by the self-help groups can help to explain the influence of the self- help group in marketing empowerment among women-owned businesses.

7. IMPLICATION

In the current study, the self-help group is found to be significant in influencing marketing empowerment among business women. This implies that the self-help groups are an instrument for women empowerment. The explanation of why the self-help groups are significant in promoting market empowerment tends to differ from one context to another. This mean that the self-help group and empowerment can be explained using different indicator variables based on time to time and based on one context to another context.

8. RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER STUDY

This study was conducted in the Shinyanga Region of Tanzania. It is limited to one region of Tanzania. It is further suggested that future studies be carried out in other regions other than

Shinyanga. It is also suggested that further studies be carried out in more than one region of Tanzania.

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